

Provision of Security-as-a-Service (SecaaS) in Lightweight Scenarios

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Abstract—The Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) landscape is nowadays crippled by cybersecurity threats and criminal attacks. Despite being a critical asset of any country’s economy, cybersecurity protection of the SMEs is often overlooked due to lack or both financial and human resources and knowledge in the field. To this end, this paper reports on the authors’ development in the H2020-EU project called “Practical Autonomous Cyberhealth for resilient SMEs & Microenterprises” (PALANTIR). It intends to offer protection and security to SMEs and Micro Enterprises (MEs) with the implementation of multiple Security Capabilities (SCs), composed of Security-as-a-Service (SecaaS) solutions to protect them with monitoring and reacting duties. This paper provides a first approach of the design and implementation of the SCs designed to provide affordable SecaaS, taking into account the current status of the development.

Index Terms—SecaaS, Security Capabilities, Monitoring and Remediation, SME/MEs

Tipo de contribución: *Investigación en desarrollo*

I. INTRODUCTION

The new scenarios appeared in the recent years imply a real change in the form of implementing and protecting the security and data privacy of the organizations. In this task, the resources (assets, budget, worker education, etc.) available by such entities have a great importance, and unfortunately there is a remarkable inequality among all of them. Considering large enterprises, they usually have in their staff experts in cybersecurity and implement the most recent technologies to protect their assets and processes. Nonetheless, the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are the main targets of the cyber criminals, due to the lack of resources that these organizations have in protecting their organization and assets. Therefore, there is a critical need in the protection of the SMEs to address the current threats that they are suffering [1].

Advances in the technologies used to implement security and data privacy also are a challenge for SMEs, because they require specific skills not widely available. For instance, technologies like Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Virtualization, IoT, and Big Data, are some of the recent technologies gradually adopted by the enterprises in the current scene [2]. Focusing on SMEs, the virtualization technology can allow them to use fewer resources and efforts for reaching successful actions, thereby reducing capital expenditure (CAPEX) and maximising operational expenditures (OPEX).

On the other hand, a new tendency so-called Security-as-a-Service (SecaaS) is appearing in the recent years in order to provide affordable security knowing the needs and resources that possible targets of this protection method have [3]. In the SME context, different SecaaS solutions are available in the literature trying to improve and protect the environment of these critical organizations [4].

Building upon this scenario, the H2020-EU project called “Practical Autonomous Cyberhealth for resilient SMEs & Microenterprises” (PALANTIR) [5] aims to protect SMEs and Micro Enterprises (MEs) by applying Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technology to implement Security and Data Privacy as-a-Service. These secure services will be the main enabler in ensuring compliance with the Security Capabilities (SCs) necessary for the protection of any SME/ME. In this vein, this paper presents the design of the first collection of SCs delivered in PALANTIR, composed of specific SecaaS solutions for monitoring and reaction, as well as the proposed architecture and their implementation.

In addition, the PALANTIR project consists of other components: a Threat Intelligence component, with Machine and Deep Learning support to spot complex threats; a Risk Management Framework to perform risk assessments of SME/ME clients and provide more specific SCs; an SC Orchestrator to manage the SC lifecycle and actions available in the SC; and other components which are not as relevant to this paper. Further information regarding PALANTIR components and functionalities may be found at [5].

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II includes the design and creation of the SCs architecture with the technologies, subcomponents, and interfaces defined. Section III explains the implementation details, showing the technology used, structure defined, and the specific code details to create an SC. And finally, Section IV summarises the content presented in this paper of work-in-progress and explains the next steps and open fronts.

II. DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

Before defining SC, the NFV technology must be presented as one of its key enablers. This technology defines the Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) which are virtualised services deployed in computing platforms running in dedicated hardware technology. Typically, VNF is named for the use of Virtual Machines in their developing, and Container Network Functions (CNFs) [6] for the use of container technology. This last can be understood as a subset of VNFs where the technology applied in the implementation and deployment is the containerisation. If both technologies want to be named, the xNF nomenclature is selected. This technology has achieved a widely use in the recent solutions that are being deployed in virtualization scenarios, thanks to the lightweight use of resources and the interoperability offered. The SC is defined as the implementation of xNF technology to provide SecaaS solutions with an optimised use of the limited resources and knowledge that clients of the PALANTIR platform will have.

Figure 1. The architecture of a Security Capability.

The SC design and architecture is presented in Figure 1, where different subcomponents are presented:

- Virtual Deployment Unit (VDU): Allocated inside of the corresponding xNF, which includes the security service implemented in the form of a container. The VDU is the logic of the SC and defines the security character of the SC. One or more VDUs can be chained and connected by a given Virtual Link (VL), which manages the internal connectivity of the SC. Besides, the service can have implemented different actions that can be performed, such as reconfiguration, start commands, stop commands, etc., which shall be executed by the Orchestrator component belonging to the PALANTIR project.
- Security Element Manager (SEM) acts as an intermediary between the security service implemented and external components outside the SC. Mainly, the SEM exposes the data generated or collected in the services deployed in the SC. Furthermore, it is responsible for managing the SC lifecycle and security configurations through the communication with the Orchestrator component. Thanks to this component, the service configuration is abstracted for all external components that want to interact with the SC and manages the data privacy in an efficient way since certain data would be private in the SC context.
- The service implemented in a VDU contains the logic of a given security mechanism, such as a Firewall, an Intrusion Detection System (IDS), etc. The PALANTIR project pretends to offer the possibility of uploading new services created by other developers.
- Network Service (NS) is the most external subcomponent that the SC has in order to allocate all VDUs and the SEM inside. This can be understood as the wrapper of the SC. At the end, such NS is the element that finish to be instantiated by the Orchestrator.
- SC chain: Under the NS domain, more than one SC can be chained in order to provide a much more complete SecaaS solution with different characteristics given from each SC deployed. For example, a NS could contain a reacting SC with a monitoring SC allowing to join both characteristics in one SecaaS solution.

In addition, any SC exhibits two interfaces. First, it has a direct connection with the Orchestrator (*VeNf-Vnfm*), since this component is in charge of the lifecycle management of the SC. The Orchestrator has the responsibility for instantiating, managing, stopping, and deleting the SCs which are deployed. In addition, the Orchestrator is the input point to activate the actions available in the SCs so as to reconfigure and change the SecaaS services running on them. Besides, the SEM allows SC to transfer records and data collected with the services implemented, for instance, NetFlow records collected by a service or a log created by an IDS. This interface might be proven effective to detect possible threats which can be acting in real time in the SME/ME infrastructure. In this case, the SEM does not need the connection with the Orchestrator because it can directly forward the information collected to the Threat Intelligence into the PALANTIR platform. The second interface (*Ve-Nf*) is the connection between the NFV Infrastructure (NFVI), where the SCs will be deployed.

Thanks to the virtualization technologies, the SCs might contain multiple security services, allowing the creation of a catalogue with different SC types that will be offered by the PALANTIR project. In this context, two large families are contemplated: the monitoring and reacting families. The monitoring family covers all security services which collect information and detect possible anomalous activities in the organization. The reacting family involves the mechanisms that stop and mitigate the threats previously detected, as well as the protection from non-produced attacks. Besides, each family can accommodate different types of SCs. In the first iteration of the PALANTIR project, the following types have been addressed to date:

- Intrusion Detection System (IDS): The IDS SC covers the threat detection techniques. There are two primary threat detection techniques: *signature-based* detection and *anomaly-based* detection. The former uses known characteristics of different cyber-attacks to recognise the threat produced, while the latter stores the normalised baseline and generates an alert when detecting an unknown behaviour or activity.
- Deep Packet Inspection (DPI): the DPI SC develops the

characteristics required to inspect IP packets. So, the DPI can be compared with an IDS since it performs traffic analysis and detects anomalous messages.

- Network NetFlow Sniffer (NNS): This SC can be implemented to support other components, both PALANTIR or external components. The NNS SC collects the traffic passing through it, converts it to NetFlow records, and sends it to an intermediate (e.g., Kafka) message broker. The components interested in such NetFlow records can obtain them through the specific broker channel.
- Firewall (FW): The FW SC is a key security service belonging to the reacting family, because traffic filtering turns out to be one of the most widely used security mechanisms in mitigating a threat. Besides, a FW SC offers integrated protection of the network environment through packet filtering, load balancing, and firewall rules created to avoid and mitigate malicious activities occurring to the organisation domain.

III. IMPLEMENTATION OF SECURITY SERVICES

A complete review of the available solutions has been performed to implement the design and the architecture presented in Section II. Regarding this, the technology supported by the Orchestrator component is the key part of this researching, because this component mainly works with Virtual Machines and Containers. Between both, PALANTIR decides to use container technology to provide a lightweight solution. Therefore, Kubernetes (K8s) [7] is the selected technology for the deployment of SCs since the Orchestration component, which is implemented with Open Source MANO (OSM) software, only supports this technology.

Nevertheless, Kubernetes is the managing software for the containers, but the creation of the involved images inside of the containers are required. In this context, Docker [8] is the low-level technology used for the creation and implementation of the images that will be subsequently deployed in Kubernetes thanks to OSM. Docker provides the operating system images where it is possible to add the commands to customise and implement the specific SC image. The definition of these technologies allows developers to have a common base for the development of new SCs.

On the other hand, other components of PALANTIR can execute actions in the SCs in order to reconfigure the SC in execution time via:

- *day-0 actions*: they are understood as the tasks needed before instantiating the SC, for example, user/password creation, SSH keys establishment, etc.
- *day-1 actions*: are executed where the SC is already deployed. These actions are related to install packages, execute commands, etc.
- *day-2 actions*: These are referred to on-demand actions, such as real-time actions.

For the implementation of these actions, OSM presents two technology possibilities:

- Helm Charts [9]: It offers a way to package a collection of Kubernetes resources. Thanks to this, more complex Kubernetes deployments can be performed in a simple way, allowing OSM to abstract the low-level definitions that Kubernetes needs to create a container. Nonetheless,

```
FROM ubuntu:20.04
ENV DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive
RUN apt-get update -y && apt-get install python3 python3-pip wget -y
RUN apt-get install gcc openssl libssl-dev bison flex libndnet autoconf libtool -y
RUN apt-get install libpcap-dev -y
RUN apt-get install libnghttp2-dev -y
RUN apt-get install libdumbnet-dev -y
RUN apt-get install libpcrc3-dev zlib1g-dev libluajit-5.1-dev -y
RUN wget https://www.snort.org/downloads/snort/daq-2.0.7.tar.gz
RUN wget https://www.snort.org/downloads/snort/snort-2.9.19.tar.gz
RUN tar xvzf daq-2.0.7.tar.gz
RUN tar xvzf snort-2.9.19.tar.gz
WORKDIR /daq-2.0.7
RUN autoreconf -f -i
RUN ./configure && make && make install
WORKDIR /snort-2.9.19
RUN ./configure --enable-sourcefire && make && make install
RUN ldconfig
RUN ln -s /usr/local/bin/snort /usr/sbin/snort
RUN mkdir -p /etc/snort/rules
RUN mkdir /var/log/snort
RUN mkdir /usr/local/lib/snort_dynamicrules
RUN touch /etc/snort/rules/white_list.rules
RUN touch /etc/snort/rules/black_list.rules
RUN touch /etc/snort/rules/local.rules
RUN cp etc/*conf* /etc/snort
RUN cp etc/*map /etc/snort
RUN alias python=python3
WORKDIR /opt/filebeat
RUN wget https://artifacts.elastic.co/downloads/beats/filebeat/filebeat-7.13.3-amd64.deb
RUN dpkg -i filebeat-7.13.3-amd64.deb
COPY ./filebeat.yml /etc/filebeat/filebeat.yml
COPY ./portscanning.rules /etc/snort/rules/local.rules
RUN filebeat modules enable snort
```

Figure 2. The Snort Dockerfile.

Helm Charts only permits the implementation of day-0 and day-1 actions.

- Juju Charms [10]: It implements a charmed operator framework to deploy, integrate, and manage Kubernetes containers and Virtual Machine (VM) natives applications, as well as the implementation of both day-0, day-1, and day-2 actions. This software needs a controller allocated in the Kubernetes cluster to deploy SCs and execute actions. OSM automatically creates the controller in a transparent way for the user. Besides, an operator (another container) is created along with the SC container to manage the actions that the developer has implemented in the definition of the charm for the SC.

After presenting the selection technologies, the showcase of an SC with the implementation of an IDS is presented in detail to see the different parts and elements needed to develop a new one. The full code presented here is publicly available in the official PALANTIR GitHub repository [11], which currently is in a work-in-progress state. Regarding SC creation, the first step is the creation of the docker image. In this case, the docker image corresponds to the preparation of the Snort IDS software [12]. Essentially, this step covers the development and testing of the Dockerfile with the commands required for the correct deployment and installation of the Snort IDS software in Ubuntu 20.04 operating system. In Figure 2, the content of the Snort IDS Dockerfile is presented.

The Dockerfile contains the commands needed to correctly install and configure the Snort IDS software. In addition, the Dockerfile includes the installation of the Filebeat software [13], the specific implementation of the SEM element (explained above), which is in charge of collecting the monitoring data generated in the SC. The SEM part involved in the communication with orchestration part is shown below.

In the current status, the docker image compiled from the Dockerfile and created in the local environment must be uploaded to the DockerHub [14], the official public repository

```

snort
├── actions.yaml
├── config.yaml
├── charmcraft.yaml
├── metadata.yaml
├── requirements-dev.txt
├── requirements.in
├── requirements.txt
├── run_tests
├── snort_ubuntu-20.04-amd64.charm
├── src
│   └── charm.py
└── test_charm.py

```

Figure 3. The Snort charm structure.

where many developers upload their images to be retrieved by the docker technology in the deployment moment, in order to be reachable in a next step when the charm is implemented. In a future state, the SC image will be allocated in a repository belonging to the PALANTIR infrastructure.

With the SC image created, the next step is the implementation of the Snort charm, the wrapper element that allows the docker image to be deployed into a Kubernetes cluster, as well as the development of different actions which can be executed into the SC image. The Snort IDS charm is composed by different files. In Figure 3, the structure of the Snort IDS charm is presented.

Inspecting the content presented in Figure 3, the files that can be highlighted are:

- *metadata.yaml*: The definition of the charm is indicated by the charm type (VM or K8s), the name, the creator, the description, the image resource (DockerHub repository), and the deployment type of Kubernetes (NodePort, LoadBalancer).
- *charmcraft.yaml*: This file is added in the recent versions of the Juju charm definition and includes the operating system base of the image (e.g., Ubuntu 20.04 LTS).
- *config.yaml*: The configuration parameters that the image needs in the instantiation time are defined in this file. For example, SSH keys used for remote connection, user and password of certain service required in the starting point.
- *actions.yaml*: This file defines the actions that can be triggered in the charm with the list of parameters, their format type (string, integer, boolean), the action name, and the description.
- *src/charm.py*: The “src” folder contains the key part of the charm, i.e., the code developed with the charm logic. The *charm.py* contains the different methods that define the charm, such as the K8s specification, action methods with the code needed to perform the action, etc.
- **.charm*: This file is the compression of the charm ready to be instantiated by the Orchestrator component. This file compresses all dependencies, libraries, and code that the charm needs to run in a correct form. It is the output of the command *charmcraft pack*.

With all content presented, the Snort IDS charm is ready for the instantiation and deployment in the K8s infrastructure. Executing the deployment, two containers are instantiated: one for the SC image and one with a Juju charm operator. The latter implements the communication with the orchestration part and the correct execution of the actions developed in the Snort IDS charm code, making up the second part of the SEM element together with the Filebeat software.

IV. CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

In this paper, the criticality of the cybersecurity in the case of SMEs has been presented and the possible solution for the issues that such organizations suffer in this term. For that, the purpose, design, and implementation of the Security Capabilities defined in PALANTIR project have been presented. Thanks to this solution, different advantages are provided to SME/MEs, such as the affordable protection provided with a reduction of costs and resources, the lack of technical knowledge needed to implement the PALANTIR solution and the customisation of the solution offered (list of SCs) depending of each SME/ME requirements.

Different things are still pending to do and implement in the PALANTIR project. For instance, the SC catalogue needs to be extended with more types of SCs like a virtual Terminal Access Point to allow port mirroring, a Virtual Private Network to offer private communications for the SME clients, etc. Besides, the SCs must be attested in order to manage the integrity of such SC and detect anomalous behaviours inside it. Therefore, different mechanisms to provide a correct attestation of SCs will be implemented, such as the state of binary files and the checking of the services correctly executed into the SC. With regard to the IDS SC, it generates alerts when a cyber-attack is detected. These alerts should be incorporated into the Threat Intelligence component, which contains Machine and Deep Learning mechanisms to detect cyber-attacks and such alerts could help to provide a further stronger detection.

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